

Gender and Sexuality Oscar Wilde

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Abstract

In the paper, the novel The Picture of Dorian Gray, written by Oscar Wilde and the film Dorian Gray (2009), directed by Oliver Parker, are analyzed. This paper aims to present an answer to the question on how the story of this novel has changed through the impact of the pornification of the news on the film alteration of the movie in terms of coition and entre. Through the analysis of characters, events, literary and cinematographic techniques from a laid and coitus point of view it has become evident that the novel adheres to prudish intercourse roles and ideas on dalliance the pornification of the news has made it possible to highlight the sexual subtext of the book in the film. Conventions in of both sexes are broken in the movie, which has led to entrust women and more feminine men. Additionally, the switching gazes and the more validation characters in the film have resulted in a more enjoyable story for contemporary audience rivaled to the story in the novel.

Keywords: pornification, gender roles, news, sexuality.

Introduction

Oscar Wilde first published *The Picture of Dorian Gray* as a short story in 1890; his prim readers were shocked by the glutton lifestyle of Dorian Gray and the homosexual subtext of the text. The novel describes the story of the young and beautiful Dorian Gray. In 2009 Oliver Parker directed the film starring Ben Barnes as Dorian Gray and Colin Firth as Lord Henry Wotton. This modern film accustom of the novel is "rated R for sexual content, including nudity violence and some drug use." Between the prissy times and 2014 ideas on insemination and equity have changed immensely. Lord Henry has a wife; however, he uses all his time with Dorian mentoring him.

The incorporation of sex scenes rather of other views to amuse the audience is a result of the pornification of the news. The idea of 'pornification,' a term invented by Brian McNair in 1996, is also known as 'pornographication' or 'sexualisation' of illustrates how filth infiltrates and proliferates through our news. This paper draws on theory from attunement studies, gender studies, and news studies. For young people, their image and anticipation of love and sex. For example, children have also become widespread. The most criticized aspect of the pornification is the feminist issue.

The Picture of Dorian Gray

Mary Wollstonecraft's *A Vindication of the Rights of Women* the first influential feminist text was written in 1792 the woman question was not extensively agitate until the 1850s, only after that Gondor roles came into consideration. Campaigners for women's rights in the stuffy period focused mainly on practical issues such as the legal status of women education and the vote. It correlates the novel and the film in terms of fraud and coition. This will be discussed demure ideas about parity and coupling and link them to the characters and events in the play. It is essential to know how the characters are mined in the new and how they think about bear and dalliance themselves to be able to see how this is reflected in the modern refit.

According to Martin Danahay, the victories period showed a most extreme form of produce segregation with strict separate spheres for men and women. This hatch segregation was reinforced through images, texts that implicitly, explicitly stated that work was manly and therefore not appropriate for women. W.E.H. Lecky and John Stuart Mill both published influential works on the women question in 1869. Lecky was a historian and Mill a philosopher they both saw the origin of the genteel spawn roles and the subjection of women as a result of man's physical strength which was needed in the barbarian world. Lecky also argued that women were the slaves of men as "her life is one of continual, abject and unrequited toil" and "she is exposed to all the violent revulsions of feelings that follow among rude men the gratification of animal passion." For example, an anonymous reviewer of *The Times* stated that "the most interesting side of a woman's character is her relation to the other sex and the errors of women that are most interesting spring out of this relation."

First of all, when reading the play in a beget studies mindset, the absence of women is striking. The innovative is focalized from a male perspective the focalizes being most often Henry, Dorian, and Basil, and Sibyl Vane only once. Women are rarely mentioned or spoken about in the novel. The only female character of importance to the story is Sibyl Vane, Dorian's first love. The first time a woman is mentioned in the book; Basil describes Lady Brandon as having a "curiously shrill voice" to which Lord Henry replies that "she is a peacock in everything except beauty." The next instance where a woman is mentioned, Henry says that "women have no appreciation of good looks.

My dear boy, no woman, is a genius. Women are a decorative sex. They never have anything to say, but they say it charmingly. Women represent the triumph of matter over mind, just as men represent the triumph of spirit over morals.

In the novel is mainly focused on the lives of Dorian and Henry and told from their perspectives. The men are often at home or a bar drinking amongst themselves, and they only meet women at parties. Henry does not work, and neither does his wife, so they must be at home most of the time. Henry mentions that all his friends' acquaintances and enemies are male. Dorian's quick switch between objectification and hate for Sibyl and Henry mentioning that every one of worth he knows is male also illustrates how irrelevant women are according to the men in the novel.

The separation of the male and female spheres in the movie is striking, and the individual characters show different attitudes towards the empress definitions of the sire. This is strengthened through the erogenous descriptions of his beauty: scarlet lips golden hair and eternal youth. Precise believed in the Rousseau an idea that children were born pure and free of sin and would grow up well unless they were spoiled by grown-ups. Dorian is the only heir of the vast fortune he does not have to work; he only manages his staff. He spends his days with Henry and his other male friends, and he reads and travels a lot.

Basil Halward is a painter and a close friend of Henry and Dorian. Basil is controlled with Dorian's beauty, and after painting Dorian as romantic figures from mythology, he paints the

picture of him. Basil is not a feminine character. Because he has a job, he is the most masculine character of the upper class, according to Danahay's definition of masculinity. Sibyl Vane is the beautiful young actress Dorian falls in love with and the most influential female character in the novel. Sibyl becomes an object of desire and loses herself in her love for him. She is objectified but also objectifies herself by putting herself entirely in Dorian's power and killing herself when he breaks up with her. She is not a strong woman at all. She could be seen as a stereotypical priggish woman as she is entirely dependent on the men in her life.

James Vane is Sibyl's protecting older brother. They do not have a father anymore; thus, he has taken over the masculine role of protecting the family. He is part of the lower class and does manual labor as a sailor. It is clear from the novel that he has committed sins these sins are not explicitly mentioned. Throughout the novel author has kept quiet about the protagonist's sins, but it is clear from the public humiliation he experiences that his sins are worse than just self-preoccupation. Except for her great love for him and the hints of unspeakable crimes he has committed the novel does not speak of whoopee. He is accused of "creeping at dawn out of dreadful houses and slinking in disguise into the foulest dens in London," supposedly strange things happen at his country house. As an explanation of what sins he committed precisely, the author stated that "each man sees his sin in him. What his sins are no-one knows. He who finds them has brought them" Because no sin is specifically mentioned readers try to find their sin in the novel.

According to Heilmann and Llewellyn "the 2009 film version of the novel directed by Oliver Parker, To see the changes between novel and film this will be analysed and compared in the film and confront these findings to the analysis of the book. This paper is built up in much the same way as the previous one: an overview of coitus and propagation in modern society will be given first, then the film will be analyzed. A lot has changed about mating and procreation between puritan times and now. These changes are part of a greater shift of comfort in social relations as contemporary relations between men and women and adults and children have become "more relaxed, egalitarian and open." Sex has become more of an adventure; one-night stands, filth, and sex toys are accepted by Western society.

This paper looks-up the play has changed through the influence of the pornification of the news on the film makeover in terms of for course and femme. Most probably the addition of sex scenes a result of the pornification of the report, the invention of the new character Emily Wotton, a consequence of changed inequities roles will have the most influence on the story. By looking at the novel and the film from this point of view, it is possible to gain new insights on the original book but also about the timelessness of the story, about contemporary issues such as race and sexuality.

Homosexuality and womenfolk studies are often grouped nowadays, he and she are probably homosexual characters, but they are just as sexist as Lord Henry Wotton. The lower class people the Vanes do fit well in the traditional Vittoria nookie roles through their work and status. The exact sins Dorian commits are not mentioned, and mainly congress is not spoken about explicitly. However, his crimes do get punished in the end; this agrees with dainty rules of morality.

Conclusion

In conclusion of the story adheres to epicene chicks roles and ideas on coition. While the novel only hints at the nature of his sins, the sex scenes in the movie have given his sins an interpretation. Also, the homosexual subtext of the novel has been made specific through the addition of sexually explicit scenes. It was initially expected that the addition of Emily Wotton would be the most significant change in the film; this is not the case. She is primarily a love interest who happens to be a feminist character.

In the paper focus on Oscar Wilde's homosexuality and femininity and how this is represented in the novel, very few sources focus exclusively on carnality and equitable in the book. Furthermore, the only sources on the film are reviews by film critics. For example, the highly praised acclimation from 1945 has incorporated contemporary ideas on copulation and unisex how these parallel to the novel this will also demonstrate the differences in conceptions of kindof and copulating between 1945 and now. Das Bildnis des Dorian Gray and conformation from 1970 is considered a soft-porn film and the comparison of this film to Dorian Gray might show whether or not the pornofication of the news has resulted in that modern mainstream films are just as explicit as soft porn in the seventies.

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